

HIGH-TEMPERATURE IMINISATION FOR CRYSTALLINE POLY(ARYL ETHER KETONES): NEW PRECURSOR-RESINS FOR THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A new high-temperature iminisation reaction for the direct derivatisation of crystalline poly(aryl ether ketones) has been successfully developed, resulting in their conversion to amorphous polymers and so improving their solubility for long-fibre impregnation. Hydrolysis of the imine groups regenerates crystalline polyketones.

Keywords: Poly(aryl ether ketones); Chemical modification; New resins; Thermoplastic composites; Iminisation.

INTRODUCTION

The interest in chemical modification of semi-crystalline poly(aryl ether ketones), PAEK's, to facilitate their use as matrices in carbon fibre reinforced composites, has grown significantly in recent years [1-4]. The aim is to synthesise amorphous, soluble PAEK derivatives which would be easier to impregnate and allow subsequent regeneration of the original polyketone, without affecting its valuable properties.

Amongst other studies, the synthesis of poly(aryl ether ketimines) from imine monomers has been reported [2-4]. However, only one attempt to *directly* functionalise PAEK's with appropriate amines has been described [5]. A high-temperature (220-240 °C) reaction of PEEK with *p*-phenylene-diamine in diphenylsulfone (DPS) was employed. Here however the aim was to increase the modulus of PEEK by cross-linking, hence a cross-linking diamine was used and an insoluble, amorphous PEEK ketimine was synthesized.

In the present work, non-cross-linkable amines were investigated, in order to generate amorphous, soluble PAEK ketimine derivatives. As long as this step was successful, it was then planned to reverse the reaction, i.e. cleave the ketimine group, while retaining, if possible, all the valuable properties of the polyketone intact.

EXPERIMENTAL

All commercially available materials were of analytical grade and were used as received. PEEK was provided by Cytac Engineered Materials UK Ltd. ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DPX 250 MHz spectrometer at 250 MHz

and 62.5 MHz, respectively, using CDCl₃, with TMS as internal standard. Melting points and glass transition temperatures were determined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) with a Mettler Toledo DSC20 instrument under a nitrogen atmosphere at 10 or 20 °C/min. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer FT1700 spectrophotometer (thin films from chloroform solutions or KBr pellets).

Synthesis of new PAEK ketimine derivatives using 2,2-diphenylethylamine (2,2-DPEA) and 3,3-diphenylpropylamine (3,3-DPPA)

PEEK (0.577 g, 2.0 mmol) was placed in a glass reactor equipped with a nitrogen inlet and an overhead stirrer, together with diphenylsulfone (9.0 g, 41 mmol) and a) 2,2-diphenylethylamine (1.972 g, 10 mmol) or b) 3,3-diphenylpropylamine (2.113 g, 10 mmol). The reactor was placed in a sand bath. The system was purged with nitrogen and the temperature was raised slowly (90 °C/h) to 315 °C. Immediately upon reaching 315 °C, the temperature was lowered to 270 °C and kept stable for 3 h. A homogenous, bright orange/yellow solution was formed. After 3 h, the hot reaction mixture was poured on an aluminum tray and left to cool. Subsequently, the flaky light-brown product was dissolved in dichloromethane (100 ml) and the polymer was reprecipitated in methanol (300 ml). Off-white/yellow powders were recovered after filtration in both cases. These were subsequently washed with refluxing methanol and dried at 80 °C for 3h (a: 0.83 g, 89% yield; b: 0.92 g, 96% yield). The reactions worked equally well even when omitting the initial peak temperature at 315 °C and stabilising the temperature at 270 °C from the beginning. PEK also reacted smoothly under the same conditions, yielding the corresponding derivatives.

PEEK-2,2-DPEA derivative: IR $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 3026 (-C-H-), 2914 (-C-H-), 1599 (-C=N-), 1491 (-C-C-), 1223 (-C-O-C-), 1164 (-C-CO-C-); ¹H-NMR (250 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{H} (ppm) = 7.42-7.39 (2H, m, H_e), 7.25-6.84 (20H, m, H_b, H_d, H_p, H_o, H_k, H_l, H_m), 4.58-4.53 (1H, H_i, tr, J = 5 Hz), 4.08-4.05 (2H, H_h, d, J = 7.5 Hz); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{C} (ppm) = 167.2 (C_g), 159.3 (C_q), 157.9 (C_c), 152.3 (C_a), 143.4 (C_j), 135.2 (C_f), 130.9 (C_n), 130.1 (dd, C_e, C_o), 128.5 (C_k), 128.3 (C_l), 126.2 (C_m), 121.1 (dd, C_b), 117.5 (dd, C_d, C_p), 58.8 (C_h), 52.6 (C_i); η_{inh} (CHCl₃) = 0.25 dL/g; T_g (onset) = 128 °C; GPC (RI, THF): M_n = 45,700, M_w = 82,400; Elemental analysis for C₃₃H₂₅O₂N: % Theoretical: C 84.77, H 5.39, N 2.99; % Found: C 84.27, H 5.37, N 3.01.

PEEK-3,3-DPPA derivative: IR $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 3025 (-C-H-), 2934 (-C-H-), 1599 (-C=N-), 1491 (-C-C-), 1222 (-C-O-C-), 1165 (-C-CO-C-); ¹H-NMR (250 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{H}

(ppm) = 7.61-7.56 (2H, m, H_e), 7.30-6.91 (20H, m, H_b, H_d, H_p, H_q, H_l, H_m, H_n), 4.14-4.08 (1H, tr, H_j, J = 7.5 Hz), 3.37-3.31 (2H, tr, H_h, J = 7.5 Hz), 2.46-2.37 (2H, q, H_i, J = 7.5 Hz); ¹³C-NMR (62.5 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_c (ppm) = 167.3 (C_g), 159.8 (C_r), 158.1 (C_c), 152.8 (C_a), 145.2 (C_k), 135.5 (C_f), 131.5 (C_o), 130.5 (dd, C_e, C_p), 128.8 (C_l), 128.4 (C_m), 126.3 (C_n), 121.3 (dd, C_b), 118.1 (dd, C_d, C_q), 52.3 (C_h), 49.1 (C_j), 37.3 (C_i); η_{inh} (CHCl₃) = 0.32 dL/g; T_g (onset) = 112 °C; GPC (RI, THF): M_n = 47,000, M_w = 83,500; Elemental analysis for C₃₄H₂₇O₂N: % Theoretical: C 84.80, H 5.65, N 2.91; % Found: C 84.69, H 5.63, N 2.82.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of new PAEK ketimine derivatives

Reactions of PEEK and PEK with 2,2-diphenylethylamine (2,2-DPEA) and 3,3-diphenylpropylamine (3,3-DPPA) at 270 °C for 3 h in DPS as solvent (Scheme 1) proved to be quite successful for the synthesis of a new family of poly(aryl ether ketimines). The rationale for the use of those two amines, apart from their commercial availability and low volatility, derived directly from their aliphatic/aromatic structure. The amine group is attached to the aliphatic chain and thus should show increased reactivity compared to aniline derivatives, whilst the aromatic segment would help provide the required stability to avoid degradation under the reaction conditions. In addition, the use of a mono-functional amine should not induce cross-linking to the system. Characterisation by ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR, IR and DSC was consistent with an amorphous polymer bearing the C=N double bond and the flexible aliphatic/aromatic side-chain of the specific amines employed (Table 1).

Table 1. Properties of PEEK and PEK imine derivatives

Entry	Sample	T _g (onset) (°C)	M _n (RI, THF)	M _w (RI, THF)	T _m (°C)	η _{inh} in CHCl ₃ (dL/g)
1	PEEK-2,2-DPEA imine	128	27,800	49,300	-	0.25
2	PEEK-3,3-DPPA imine	112	21,400	45,300	-	0.32
3	PEK-2,2-DPEA imine	130	21,600	42,300	-	0.24
4	PEK-3,3-DPPA imine	109	17,300	35,600	-	0.25

The new poly(aryl ether ketimines) were found to be soluble in a wide selection of organic solvents, including DCM, CHCl_3 , THF, DMAc, DMF and NMP, insoluble in water, MeOH, DMSO and CH_3CN and only swollen in acetone.

The study of the thermal properties of the new ketimine polymers showed that all of them were amorphous, exhibiting T_g values in the region between 109 – 130 °C and degrading at temperatures above 360 °C. For the same polymer, derivatives coming from 2,2-DPEA exhibited higher T_g 's than their counterparts deriving from 3,3-DPPA of approximately 20 °C. This could be attributed to the longer aliphatic chain of the 3,3-DPPA derivatives, which makes the side-chain more flexible and thus lowers the T_g of the polymer. The viscosity and molecular weight data were within the expected range for similar PEEK derivatives [6]. Finally, elemental analysis confirmed the incorporation of nitrogen into the structure, giving C, H and N experimental values close to the theoretical ones.

Scheme 1. Reactions of PEEK and PEK with 2,2-DPEA and 3,3-DPPA

The DSC curves for PEEK-2,2-DPEA and PEEK-3,3-DPPA can be seen in Figures 1 and 2, respectively.

Figure 2. DSC curve for PEEK-2,2-DPEA

Figure 3. DSC curve for PEEK-3,3-DPPA

Attempted hydrolysis of PEEK-2,2-DPEA and PEEK-3,3-DPPA

The first priority after characterizing the new ketimine derivatives was to attempt the deprotection of these polymers, to regenerate the starting polyketone. This would prove that the new high-temperature iminisation can be utilized as a reversible tool in high-performance polymer composite applications. Several ways of deprotecting similar structures have been reported [2-4], the majority of which involved an acid-catalyzed

hydrolytic route. The reactions took place either heterogeneously, by maintaining the fine polymeric powder under reflux in an aqueous acidic solution (either in an autoclave or at ambient pressure), or homogeneously, by dissolving the polymer and then adding an appropriate amount of an aqueous acidic solution. In one case only [2] was it deduced that the hydrolysis did not affect the polymer backbone, by comparing size-exclusion chromatography results for the ketimine fractions and the corresponding deprotected ketone fractions.

Similar methodology was applied in the present work, i.e. PEEK derivatives were subjected to acid hydrolysis under homogenous and heterogeneous conditions. The routes employed were the following:

- a) Heterogeneous acid hydrolysis: maintain under reflux in a 10% aqueous methanesulfonic acid (MSA) solution for 24 hours [2]
- b) Heterogeneous acid hydrolysis: maintain under reflux in a 10% aqueous acetic acid solution for 24 hours
- c) Heterogeneous acid hydrolysis: maintain under reflux in an aqueous methanesulfonic acid (MSA) solution for 24 hours, containing the stoichiometrically required amount of acid (similar to Lindfords *et al.* [4], at ambient pressure in this case)
- d) Heterogeneous hydrolysis: maintain under reflux in water and methanol for 24 hours
- e) Homogeneous acid hydrolysis: for 24 hours at room temperature, dissolving the polymer in THF and adding 10% v/v of an aqueous 20% MSA solution [2]
- f) Homogeneous acid hydrolysis: for 24 hours at room temperature, dissolving the polymer in THF and adding the stoichiometrically appropriate amount or a five-fold acid excess, using an aqueous 20% MSA or HCl 1N solution
- g) Homogeneous acid hydrolysis: for 24 hours at room temperature, dissolving the polymer in THF and adding 10% v/v of an aqueous 20% acetic acid solution
- h) Homogeneous acid hydrolysis: for 21 hours at 50 °C, dissolving the polymer in NMP and adding an appropriate amount of an NMP/HCl 37% solution (HCl at 11.5-fold excess to polymer) [3]
- i) Basic heterogeneous hydrolysis: maintain under reflux in an 0.1 N NaOH aqueous solution for 20 hours
- j) Basic homogeneous hydrolysis: for 24 hours at room temperature, adding 10% v/v of an 0.1 N NaOH solution into a solution of the polymer in THF

Unfortunately, in no case did it prove possible to recover the starting polyketone with all its properties intact. For the majority of the acid hydrolysis routes, the NMR spectroscopic data were certainly in agreement with the expected poly(ether ether ketone) structure. However, there was always an indication of a small amount of residual polyketimine present from the spectroscopic data.

Melting points of the crystalline deprotected materials varied between 293 and 325 °C, i.e. generally much lower than expected for PEEK, suggesting lower molecular weight and crystallinity than the starting material. In several cases melting points were not found, thus the deprotection had yielded an amorphous polymer.

In the event that reasonable melting points were recorded (close to 320 °C, entries 2 and 4 of Table 2), inherent viscosity measurements in sulfuric acid followed, in order to verify if chain degradation occurred during deprotection. Indeed, viscosity values very much lower than the starting material (0.76 dL/g) were observed. All results regarding acid hydrolysis routes are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Acid hydrolysis deprotection routes

Entry	Acid hydrolysis route	T _g (onset) (°C)	T _m (°C)	η _{inh} inH ₂ SO ₄ (dL/g)	% N
1	a	150	293		-
2	b	149	327	0.34	-
3	c	155	-		2.88
4	e	150	319	0.45	-
5	f ^a	155 ^b	- ^b		0.66
		149 ^c	306 ^c		-
6	g	167	-		1.59
7	h	150	-		0.58

^a: MSA route, similar results with HCl; ^b: stoichiometric acid; ^c: 5-fold acid excess

Elemental analysis of the amorphous deprotected materials (those not showing a melting point) detected residual nitrogen, signifying incomplete cleavage of the imine functionality. For the crystalline products, nitrogen was not detected but still the thermal properties were not fully consistent with theoretical PEEK values or with each other. It seems, therefore, that even a small amount of residual ketimine, not detected by elemental analysis but indicated from ¹H-NMR and IR spectroscopy, might be adequate to suppress crystallinity and influence the thermal properties of the deprotected materials. Hence the residual traces of PEEK ketimine revealed by ¹H-NMR spectroscopic analysis might be partially inducing the observed deterioration in crystallinity, by suppressing the ability of the chain to fold and crystallize. In addition, IR spectroscopy also indicated the presence of possible residual C=N bands at approximately 1600 cm⁻¹. Furthermore, additional chain degradation processes might be occurring simultaneously with the imine group cleavage, as indicated by the very low viscosity values of the crystalline polymers in sulfuric acid. Moreover, the heterogeneous deprotection in water and methanol afforded a partially deprotected product. Finally, the basic hydrolysis routes showed little evidence of successful deprotection either.

To investigate these results further, selected specimens that exhibited crystalline polymer behaviour in terms of their thermal properties, were studied by gel permeation chromatography (GPC). Entries 2 and 4 of Table 2 were included. A characteristic set of data for the starting PEEK polymer and the corresponding protected-then-deprotected polymers, using different deprotection routes, are shown in Table 3 and Figure 3.

Table 3. Characterisation of selected deprotected imine derivatives of PEEK

Entry	Sample	Acid hydrolysis route	T _g (onset) (°C)	T _m (°C)	M _n	M _w
1	Starting PEEK		144	342	28,900	81,100
2	Entry 2 of Table 2	Heterogeneous: route b	149	327	26,800	74,700
3	Entry 4 of Table 2	Homogeneous: route e	150	319	29,200	196,000
4		Homogeneous: route e	147	313	28,900	151,000
5		Homogeneous: route e	147	307	25,600	155,000

GPC analysis for molecular weight determination of the polymers was conducted in 50:50 w/w 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene:phenol at 115 °C, using a refractive index detector. The black trace is the chromatogram of the starting PEEK material, while the coloured traces correspond to entries 2-5 of Table 3.

It is obvious both from the curves and the molecular weight data of Table 3 that for all deprotected samples, the bulk of the molecular weight distribution is of lower molecular weight than the starting PEEK grade. However, three of the samples (entries 3-5) appeared to contain a small proportion of very high molecular weight component that greatly increased the weight average molecular weights. These three samples all gave yellow-coloured solution in the 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene:phenol mixture.

To compare with the molecular weight characteristics of the deprotected polyketones of Figure 3, a similar comparison between the same starting PEEK material and a protected-then-deprotected sample coming from a different chemical modification route is depicted in Figure 4. The chemical modification in this case involved the dithioacetalisation of PEEK with propane dithiol [1] and subsequently the implementation of a novel polymeric acetal exchange reaction, using ethylene glycol [7]. The latter yielded the corresponding cyclic acetal of PEEK, namely PEEK-1,3-dioxolane. This was finally hydrolysed under heterogeneous conditions and afforded deprotected PEEK. The resulting polyketone exhibited *identical* molecular weight characteristics to the starting material, thereby unambiguously confirming the reversible, non-degrading nature of this particular chemical modification. As a result, these acetal-based resins would be ideal candidates for use as matrices in carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites [7]. The acid hydrolysis of PEEK-1,3-dioxolane is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. PEEK-1,3-dioxolane acid hydrolysis route

Figure 3. GPC results-deprotected PEEK imines of Table 3 (Black trace: starting PEEK-entry 1; Blue trace: entry 2; Red trace: entry 3; Green trace: entry 4; Purple trace: entry 5)

Figure 4. Molecular weight distribution curves of starting PEEK (black trace) and PEEK coming from heterogeneous deprotection of PEEK-1,3-dioxolane (blue trace)

CONCLUSIONS

New ketimine-functionalised poly(aryl ether ketone) amorphous derivatives were synthesized by a high-temperature direct polymer derivatisation, using 2,2-diphenylethylamine and 3,3-diphenylpropylamine. The derivatives were soluble in common organic solvents and amorphous by DSC. The presence of nitrogen in the structures was confirmed by elemental analysis.

Deprotection of the imine derivatives of PEEK was not a trivial task. A wide range of acid- and base-catalysed, homogeneous and heterogeneous hydrolytic routes were investigated. Although deprotection was certainly achieved by the acid hydrolysis route, it was not possible to obtain a deprotected PEEK with all its valuable properties intact. In most cases, chemical regeneration of the carbonyl groups certainly occurred, but crystallinity and/or molecular weight were always compromised to an extent.

In the same context, other chemical modification routes that would permit the reversible derivatisation of PAEK's, to facilitate their use as composite matrices have been investigated and further developed.

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